

Review

The Effects of *Zhan Zhuang* Qigong on Mental Health: A Narrative Review.

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Abstract

Mental health is a fundamental component of overall well-being, influencing quality of life (QOL), productivity, and stress adaptation and not only the absence of mental illness. The World Health Organization argues that transforming mental health means strengthening its promotion and prevention at all stages of life and harnessing new, innovative and cost-effective tools (healthy choices, diet, breathing, exercise, arts and craft) to be adopted by the governments' health agendas and disseminated among the key environments, such homes, communities, schools and workplaces.

The effect of Traditional Chinese Exercises (TCEs) such as Tai Chi and *Qigong* has been widely studied for its physical and mental benefits. *Zhan Zhuang*, a *Qigong* practice based on maintaining static postures, has been receiving attention for promoting well-being, but its impact on mental health remains unexplored. This narrative review examines existing evidence on the effects of *Zhan Zhuang* in promoting psychological well-being.

The methodology of this review included a literature search in scientific databases such as PubMed, ScienceDirect, ResearchGate.net and Scholar.Google.pt, covering clinical studies, meta-analyses, and historical texts from Traditional Chinese Medicine. Preliminary findings suggest that *Zhan Zhuang* may reduce stress, alleviate symptoms of anxiety and depression, and enhance emotional resilience. However, methodological limitations in existing studies highlight the need for more rigorous research, including randomised clinical trials. This review underscores the potential of *Zhan Zhuang* as a complementary approach to mental health and emphasises the importance of further studies to clarify its effectiveness, mechanisms of action, and optimal practice parameters.

Keywords: Traditional Chinese Exercises; *Zhan Zhuang* Qigong; Chan-Chuang Chikung; Mental Health.

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1. Introduction

Mental health, broadly encompassing mental, emotional, social, and behavioural functions, is fundamental to individual and societal well-being, as highlighted by its definition in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders – Fifth Edition (DSM-5) as clinically significant disturbances in various mental functions^{1,2}. The global burden of mental health conditions is substantial, manifesting in significant physical, emotional, and economic challenges, including reduced work capacity and productivity³. Beyond the individual, these disorders profoundly impact families, social networks, and society at large⁴, frequently leading to direct and indirect hospital admissions⁵⁻⁷. While historically viewed as merely the absence of illness, the World Health Organization (WHO) advocates a more expansive definition of mental health as "a state of mental well-being that enables people to cope with the stresses of life, to carry out their activities, to learn and

work well, and to contribute to their community" ⁸. This perspective underscores mental health as a positive state integral to overall health and quality of life, recognising the intricate interplay of individual, social, and structural determinants ⁸. Despite its critical importance, the unmet need for mental health care remains a pressing global issue, prompting calls for increased governmental investment, integration into primary healthcare, and multisectoral policies that ensure equitable and accessible mental well-being for all ^{4,8}.

In response to this global imperative, TCEs have garnered increasing attention as complementary health interventions. These practices, developed over millennia in ancient China, seamlessly integrate movement, breathing, mental concentration, and posture to promote health, prevent disease, and support healing processes. Among the diverse forms of TCE, *Qigong* stands out as a recognised system of Chinese medicine, utilised for thousands of years to enhance both physical and psychological health ⁹⁻¹⁵. Certain *Qigong* forms, such as the "Six Healing Sounds Form" (*Liuzijue*) and "Post Standing *Qigong*" (*Zhan Zhuang gong*), can specifically target mental well-being ^{10,12}. From a therapeutic standpoint, *Qigong* is often considered a vegetative biofeedback therapy, fostering homeostasis and emotional balance by optimising *qi* circulation and modulating sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous system activity ¹⁶⁻²⁰. Its inherent simplicity, flexibility, and self-directed nature make *Qigong* a safe, accessible, and viable practice that requires no special equipment and can be performed virtually anywhere ^{21,22}. This adaptability further reduces barriers such as travel and rehabilitation costs, making it particularly beneficial for elderly individuals and those with chronic conditions, addressing both physical limitations and mental challenges ^{18,20,23-25}.

This narrative review aims to synthesise existing research on *Zhan Zhuang Qigong*, a low-intensity form of *Qigong* characterised by sustained static postures, mental adjustment, and natural breathing ²⁶. Also known as Chan-Chuang, *Zhan Zhuang* combines elements of rest and rehabilitation with gentle exercise, cultivating and mobilising vital energy (*qi*) through fixed positions held for extended periods ^{9,27}. Often described as a "mind-body" exercise due to its integration of meditation with physical activity, *Zhan Zhuang* effectively balances the autonomic nervous system, promoting cardiovascular homeostasis and physical stability ^{18,28}. Its safety profile, accessibility, and minimal adverse effects make it suitable even for individuals with cognitive deficits or clinical weakness ²⁹⁻³¹. By reviewing a range of studies, this article will follow the grounds of previous work ³² to allow for a deeper understanding of *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* therapeutic effects for mental health, complementarily providing a comprehensive overview of its potential benefits.

2. Materials and Methods

This is a narrative review of the literature to verify the effects of *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* practice on mental health and what are the main mechanisms involved. The decision to conduct a narrative review was anchored on the fact that this methodology gave us the maximum flexibility in exploring a broader range of literature.

Contrary to the systematic review, which requires very specific research questions, such as an exhaustive and highly comprehensive search across multiple databases and a rigorous selection process and quality assessment of a large volume of potential studies, the narrative review makes it possible to integrate, contextualise and provide a relevant synthesis of different types of studies.

As *Zhan Zhuang* is still a lesser-studied form of *Qigong* and a field of investigation not yet fully consolidated, where the evidence is still scarce, the narrative review presented to us the best approach to accomplish the study's objectives without compromising the feasibility of the project within the given timeframe.

A search was carried out in the PubMed database (United States National Library of Medicine), ResearchGate.net and Scholar.Google.pt. A manual search of the reference lists of the related studies was also conducted to identify additional eligible studies. The following inclusion criteria were established: (I) articles published between 1997 and 2025;

(II) clinical essay (CE) or Randomized Clinical Trial (RCT), Qualitative Study (QS); (III) published in English or Portuguese (IV) with open access to the full text and exclusion criteria: (I) duplicate studies; (II) incomplete articles; (III) works not related to the main theme. After rigorous application of these criteria, a documentary corpus composed of 38 scientific articles was selected, which constituted the theoretical basis for the development of this narrative review.

Although the authors deliberately chose to review a broader range of literature to provide a more comprehensive contextualization of the topic, strict criteria were applied in the selection of studies for the analysis of results and discussion. To ensure that only findings from studies specifically focused on *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* were included, the selection was limited to those employing static forms of *Zhan Zhuang* as an intervention technique, as well as targeting pathological conditions directly or indirectly related to mental health. This selection process resulted in the inclusion of 17 studies for analysis and discussion.

3. Results

Zhan Zhuang Qigong practices, often involving static postures such as "Cue Ball", "Holding the Ball" or "Three Circles Pose", and "Hugging the Tree", are emerging as promising interventions for mental health across a variety of populations and health conditions.

An RCT by Gonçalves *et al.*¹⁹, with 38 teachers, showed that *Zhan Zhuang* with two 10-minute sessions per week for 4 weeks significantly improved anxiety levels measured by State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI), Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) and Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS). The results suggest that *Zhan Zhuang* has the potential to improve teachers' mental health and can be implemented in schools.

Matos *et al.*¹⁷ conducted a CE with seven children who were flautists between the ages of 10 and 12 and who suffered from performance anxiety. For seven weeks, the children practised *Zhan Zhuang* techniques daily and with supervised training twice a week. The results, assessed by infrared thermography, showed that the "white ball" technique rapidly increased the rate of skin heating. And the HR decreased significantly, indicating greater relaxation and less anxiety.

Another study³³ investigated the impact of *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* was applied with a 60-minute session per week for 8 weeks, in 17 baseball players, to alleviate pre-competitive anxiety. Psychological skills for team sports were assessed through pre- and post-intervention interviews. The results indicated that *Zhan Zhuang* helped resolve tension and anxiety, increased self-efficacy, and promoted bodily changes perceived by athletes. The practice also helped them to deal with emotions more calmly and to transform negative thoughts into positive affirmations. In addition, *Zhan Zhuang* fostered self-care and a sense of unity within the team.

An RCT³⁰ in Taiwan recruited 80 patients with mild to moderate cognitive impairment. The intervention group practised *Zhan Zhuang* performing three daily 10-minute sessions, three times a week, for three months. There was an improvement in cognition in the *Zhan Zhuang* group, while the control group worsened. Muscle strength, muscle endurance, and exercise capacity increased significantly in the *Zhan Zhuang* group. Physical QOL also improved in the *Zhan Zhuang* group at the end of the study.

Moreover, an RCT by Chen *et al.*¹⁸ investigated the effects of *Qigong* on 68 stroke patients in Taiwan. Participants were divided into two groups: 33 received the *Qigong* intervention, and 35 were in the control group. *Qigong* practice was performed once a day for 15 minutes, for 10 days. Researchers assessed stroke-related neurological deficit, muscle strength, HRV, and fatigue at three time points: before the intervention began, on the fifth day, and the tenth day. The National Stroke Health Scale, the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), the Short Form-12 (SF-12), and a visual analogue scale for fatigue were used for this purpose. The results revealed that the *Qigong* group had a significantly higher QOL on the tenth day compared with the control group. Furthermore, it

was observed that neurological deficit, muscle strength, low frequency/high frequency ratio, and anxiety were significantly associated with changes in QOL. On the other hand, HR, HRV, fatigue and depression did not show a significant association with change in QOL in this study.

A prospective RCT¹¹ investigated the impact of *Qigong* on 44 nurses with high levels of burnout, divided into an intervention group (22 nurses) and a control group (22 nurses). The initial intervention consisted of two 5-minute *Qigong* sessions for 4 weeks. After this phase, participants in the intervention group performed self-practice twice a day for another 4 weeks. The main variable assessed was the levels of burnout, and secondarily, aspects of burnout, such as depersonalization and perception of personal accomplishment. All outcomes were measured using the Portuguese version of the Maslach Burnout Inventory, a 22-item questionnaire that covers the three dimensions mentioned. Post-intervention *Zhan Zhuang* group demonstrated significant differences in burnout, compared to the pre- and post-intervention results. For approximately 70% of participants, burnout levels decreased from high to moderate (55%) or low (15%). However, the dimensions of depersonalization and personal accomplishment did not show significant changes in the intervention group immediately. A follow-up assessment, 4 weeks after self-practice (8 weeks after baseline), showed no significant differences for burnout and personal accomplishment when comparing post-intervention and follow-up results. However, significant differences were found for depersonalization at this point. The study suggests that *Zhan Zhuang* is a beneficial complementary tool to alleviate burnout among nurses, appearing effective in reducing burnout and depersonalization. In light of the increased pressure and stress in hospitals due to the COVID-19 pandemic, *Qigong* may be a useful strategy to mitigate COVID-19-induced burnout, thereby improving healthcare services and capacity. Furthermore, *Qigong* has the potential to be a preventive tool that empowers nurses to deal with stressful situations, complementing other therapies and policies aimed at managing Burnout.

An RCT³⁴ with 104 high school students investigated the effect of *Zhan Zhuang* on anxiety. The students were divided into three groups: a *Zhan Zhuang* QG, a group that watched documentaries (TVD), and a group that did schoolwork (TSD). The QG group participated in seven or eight sessions of *Zhan Zhuang*, 15 to 20 minutes each, for six weeks. Anxiety was assessed using the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) and salivary cortisol tests. Although overall anxiety showed no significant differences between groups, the *Zhan Zhuang* group, which started with the highest levels of anxiety, was the only one to show a steady decreasing trend throughout the study, with a 13.7% improvement after the intervention. The *Zhan Zhuang* group also demonstrated a statistically significant reduction in anxiety levels midway through the study. The other groups showed increases or fluctuations. One noted benefit is that *Zhan Zhuang* appears to be a useful complementary tool, and no adverse events were observed in participants in the intervention group.

Another prospective RCT by Sousa *et al.*³⁵ investigated the impact of *Zhan Zhuang* in 16 transverse flute students with anxiety levels, divided into a *Zhan Zhuang* group and a control group, each with 8 students. The intervention consisted of two 30-minute sessions per week for seven weeks. The researchers assessed HR blood pressure, salivary cortisol, electrical activity of the trapezius muscle, and perception of anxiety. For this purpose, methods such as the Portuguese version of the Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (adapted for children), laboratory analysis of salivary cortisol, measurement of HRV and blood pressure by a nurse, and surface electromyography (EMG) for the trapezius muscle were used. The *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* showed a significantly greater reduction in HR. The effect of *Qigong* was even more pronounced in salivary cortisol, electrical activity of the trapezius muscle, and blood pressure. Additionally, a relevant reduction in subjective perception of anxiety was observed in the intervention group.

An RCT by Gonçalves *et al.*³⁶ investigated the impact of *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* on the cognitive function of 8th-grade adolescents aged 12 to 14. Participants practised *Zhan*

Zhuang in 5-minute sessions twice a week for 4 weeks at the end of physical education classes and were instructed to practice daily at home. Researchers assessed RT to auditory stimuli to measure attention and learning ability. Assessment methods included the STAI and salivary cortisol tests, along with an auditory task where participants pressed a button while hearing stimuli in random and rhythmic sequences. Data were collected at baseline (T0), after 2 weeks (T1), and at the beginning of the school assessment period (T2). Results showed that although RT tended to increase at T1 for all participants, the *Qigong Zhan Zhuang* group performed better, with smaller increases in RT for both types of stimuli. At T2, the increasing trend persisted in the placebo group, but the *Zhan Zhuang* group demonstrated a decrease in RT for both stimuli. This suggests that *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* may be associated with improvements in attention and learning ability.

Moreover, an RCT by Duarte *et al.*³⁷ investigated the impact of *Zhan Zhuang* on the attention of adolescents (12-14 years old). Participants were divided into groups, including a *Zhan Zhuang* group who practised for 15 minutes, three times a week, for 8 weeks. Attention levels were assessed using attention tests before the intervention and after two and four weeks. Initial results (T1) showed no differences between the groups. However, after four weeks of practice (T3), the *Zhan Zhuang* group was significantly superior in all measurable characteristics of attention compared to the control groups. The study suggests that *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* may be a useful tool to be integrated into physical education classes, and no adverse events were observed in the intervention group.

In 2017, an RCT²⁷ demonstrated that *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* is beneficial for non-Hodgkin lymphoma patients undergoing chemotherapy. Fifty participants who had completed their first cycle of chemotherapy practised a 25-minute sequence, two to three times a day, for 21 consecutive days. Researchers assessed fatigue, blood cell counts, sleep quality, and QOL. Fatigue was measured by the Brief Fatigue Inventory, sleep quality by the Verran Sleep Scale and Snyder-Halpern, and QOL according to the European Organization for Research and Treatment of Cancer Quality of Life Questionnaire (EORTC QLQ-C30). The results revealed that *Zhan Zhuang* significantly reduced the intensity and interference of fatigue, and improved patients' white blood cell count, haemoglobin levels, sleep quality, and QOL.

In another RCT, Yeh *et al.*²⁶ investigated the impact of *Zhan Zhuang* on fatigue and sleep quality in 54 patients with non-Hodgkin lymphoma receiving chemotherapy. Participants practised *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* in 20-minute sessions twice a day for 21 days, starting on the third day of the chemotherapy cycle. Researchers assessed fatigue intensity (average and worst level over the past 24 hours, on a scale of 0 to 10) and overall sleep quality using the Chinese version of the Verran and Snyder-Halpern Sleep Scale – VSHSS at the beginning and end of the program. The *Zhan Zhuang* 21-day *Qigong* program significantly improved average fatigue, worst fatigue, and overall sleep quality in patients. The difference in average fatigue between the groups was significant over time, and the *Zhan Zhuang* demonstrated a significant decrease in fatigue from pre- to post-test, indicating a time-dependent effect. Worst fatigue or exhaustion also showed a significant difference between groups over time.

Moreover, another RCT²⁹ investigated the impact of *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* breathing meditation on the QOL and interoceptive awareness of 60 breast cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy. Participants were divided into two groups: a *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* group (n=30), who practised for 35 minutes daily, 5 days a week, for 15 weeks, and a control group (n=30), who received routine care. Emotional function was assessed using the EORTC QLQ-C30 and the Multidimensional Assessment of Interoceptive Awareness (MAIA-C). The *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* program for 15 weeks has been shown to improve QOL as well as self-regulation and confidence in interoceptive awareness in breast cancer patients during chemotherapy. These results indicate a positive effect on the emotional state of patients.

As well, a CE ³⁸ investigated the impact of *Zhan Zhuang* on SD and psychological distress in breast cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy. The intervention consisted of the practice of *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* for 15 minutes to 1 hour daily for the first 21 days of the chemotherapy cycle. The study assessed SD using a 21-item symptom distress scale (a modification of the McCorkle and Young scale) and psychological distress with the revised Symptom Checklist-90. Data was collected on the day before chemotherapy started (baseline) and on days 8, 15, and 22 of treatment. Although the differences in general psychological symptoms (distress, lack of will to live, lack of hope for the future) were not statistically significant, the items "lack of will to live" and "lack of hope for the future" showed better results in the *Zhan Zhuang* experimental group.

A parallel-design RCT conducted by Li *et al.* ²⁸ investigated the benefits of *Zhan Zhuang* and resistance exercise in the rehabilitation of male methamphetamine users. Participants were divided into three groups: control (n=25), Chan-Chuang (n=26), and resistance exercise (n=25). Interventions lasted 30–40 minutes for 8 weeks. Researchers assessed the health benefits related to drug rehabilitation. Primary outcomes included drug craving (Visual Analogue Scale - VAS), mental well-being (WHO Well-Being Index-5), sleep quality (Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index - PSQI), HR, and blood pressure (OMRON U10L). Secondary outcomes measured were Body Mass Index (BMI), vital capacity, grip strength, balance, and vertical jump. The group that practised *Zhan Zhuang* demonstrated reductions in HR, DBP, and MAP. In addition, improvements in vital capacity, grip strength, and balance were observed compared with the control group. The resistance exercise group also showed reductions in SBP and MAP, as well as improvements in vital capacity, grip strength, balance, and vertical jump.

A prospective RCT conducted by Teixeira Lopes *et al.* ³⁹ investigated the effect of *Zhan Zhuang* on the auditory attention of 55 students from the University of Porto. The population with no experience in *Zhan Zhuang Qigong*, was divided into into a negative control group that watched a video, and a positive control group that practiced 5 minutes of *Zhan Zhuang Qigong*. As well, another group of students from a traditional Chinese medicine specialization program and with experience in *Zhan Zhuang Qigong*, received the intervention. The experimental groups practised *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* once a week for 50 minutes over 8 months. The study assessed RT or auditory attention under two conditions: listening to a random sound sequence with eyes closed and with eyes open with visual distraction. After the intervention, the RT of the group of *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* practitioners decreased significantly, presenting shorter RTs in both experimental conditions. This suggests a positive effect of *Zhan Zhuang* on the mechanism of sensory integration, which may be particularly relevant for people with neurodevelopmental disorders such as autism and attention deficit, and hyperactivity disorder.

A RCT conducted by Kim *et al.* ⁴⁰ investigated the effect of a *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* program in 26 patients (10 to 18 years old) with type 1 diabetes. The *Zhan Zhuang* program, lasting over 6 months, consisted of 60-minute sessions divided into 10 minutes of warm-up, 20 minutes of relaxation, 20 minutes of visualisation, and 10 minutes of closing with deep meditation and breathing. Participants were randomised into two groups with intervention switching after 24 hours. Information about diabetes, pain intensity, and emotional affect was assessed using a structured questionnaire. Pain intensity, including expected and perceived pain during blood glucose testing and insulin injections, was measured using a face pain scale. The emotional effect questionnaire, with 20 items (10 for positive effects and 10 for negative effects, such as fear and anxiety), was rated on a 5-point scale. Data was collected before and after the intervention. Analysis revealed that only the change in expected pain on insulin injection, referred to the imagined pain that participants anticipated during the procedure, was significantly different between the *Zhan Zhuang* group and the control group.

4. Discussion

According to the WHO in the World Mental Health Report, to achieve the global goals set out in the “WHO Comprehensive Mental Health Action Plan 2013-2030” and the “Sustainable Development Goals”, we need to transform our attitudes, actions and approaches to promote and protect mental health and provide and care for those in need ⁸.

Due to its holistic and preventive approach, *Zhan Zhuang*, as a mind-body practice, works to both prevent and manage mental health conditions. Unlike purely drug-based approaches, it empowers individuals to manage their well-being, offering an accessible and low-cost tool.

The 17 studies presented highlighted *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* as a promising intervention to contribute to the mental health of populations, directly aligning with the WHO call to transform attitudes and approaches in the promotion and protection of mental health.

The reviewed studies were focused on the following pathologies: anxiety (5), mental well-being –including those conducted with patients experiencing physical and emotional weakness, mostly oncology patients, which assessed effects on mental well-being such as pain management, sleep quality, fatigue, and self-confidence; attention levels (3), neurological deficits and dementia (2), and burnout (1).

The results consistently demonstrate significant reductions in anxiety, burnout and stress across a range of population groups, including teachers and chemotherapy patients. This is crucial, as chronic stress and anxiety are risk factors for more serious mental health problems. Decreased HR and salivary cortisol indicate physiological relaxation, which is essential for mental well-being.

Zhan Zhuang Qigong has been shown to significantly improve QOL, especially in patients with chronic conditions such as cancer. Improved sleep quality, reduced fatigue and increased self-efficacy contribute to an overall sense of well-being and resilience, which are essential for good mental health.

In addition, by promoting the resolution of tension and anxiety and increasing self-efficacy (perception of the ability to deal with challenges), *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* strengthens individuals’ resilience. This makes them more capable of coping with adversity and less likely to develop mental health problems in response to stressful events.

The improvement in reaction times and attention, as well as learning ability, suggests that *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* can support cognitive health. This is important for daily functioning and the ability to manage thoughts and emotions effectively.

The evidence of benefits in specific groups, such as teachers ¹⁹, who often face high levels of stress and burnout, and cancer patients ^{26,27,29,31}, who deal with intense physical and emotional challenges, demonstrates the applicability of *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* in contexts where mental health is particularly vulnerable.

Despite the mental health focus, physical improvements such as muscle strength, endurance, balance, and reduced blood pressure are intrinsic to the benefits of *Zhan Zhuang*. Good physical health is a fundamental pillar for mental health, and *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* demonstrates how the mind-body interconnection can be explored for integral well-being.

Although the objectives of the study did not focus directly on the topic of the duration of the intervention, in this narrative review, it was also interesting to note the diversity in the duration, time and frequency of the interventions. Concerning duration, the identified interventions ranged from what we call short-term, such as 10 days ¹⁸ to long-term, corresponding to interventions of 3 months or more ^{29,30,40}. Most references point to medium-term durations, with programs ranging from 4 to 12 weeks ^{11,19,26,27,29,33-35,37}.

In addition to the duration of the intervention, there is diversity in the time of practice and its frequency. The relevance of the intervention time in the results has been previously highlighted by other authors ^{19,34}, and these results seem to corroborate the limitations previously identified.

The practice of *Zhan Zhuang Qigong*, with its emphasis on body awareness and breathing, can lead to greater interoceptive awareness, which improves the ability to recognise and regulate emotions, an important part of achieving mental health.

Zhan Zhuang shows promise as a safe, accessible, and low-cost complementary approach within integrative mental health care. However, this narrative review underscores the need for more rigorous clinical trials to strengthen the evidence base and clarify its therapeutic impact. Limitations such as small sample sizes and potential observational bias—due to the difficulty of blinding and instructor presence—may affect the generalizability of current findings.

Cultural factors also present challenges to standardisation and replicability across diverse settings. Therefore, future studies should ensure standardised reporting of intervention parameters (e.g., posture type, session duration, frequency, and total length) and include medium- and long-term follow-ups to assess the persistence of effects. Comparative studies with other active interventions (e.g., mindfulness, Tai Chi, Yoga) may help determine *Zhan Zhuang's* relative efficacy.

Monitoring adherence and employing validated psychometric tools (e.g., STAI, DASS-21, BDI-II), along with physiological markers (e.g., HRV, salivary cortisol, EEG alpha waves), are strongly recommended. Additionally, investigating neurobiological mechanisms—such as BDNF expression, GABA levels, and hippocampal activity—could offer deeper insight into the underlying processes supporting its mental health benefits.

5. Conclusions

The evidence reviewed highlights *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* as a safe, accessible, and effective practice for improving mental health and overall well-being. Supported by scientifically grounded mechanisms—such as central nervous system regulation, neuroplasticity enhancement, and autonomic nervous system balance—this mind-body technique offers a low-risk, self-directed intervention for stress reduction, cognitive support, and emotional resilience. Its applicability in chronic conditions, cognitive deficits, and states of clinical weakness, as well as its relevance for athletes, students, or individuals working in high-demand environments, such as nurses or teachers, underscores its potential as a valuable complementary therapy.

Furthermore, the practice's adaptability to home, schools and workplace settings may enhance the opportunity of integrating *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* practices into public health programmes, reducing rehabilitation costs and increasing adherence. Taken together, *Zhan Zhuang Qigong* emerges as a viable and beneficial approach within integrative health strategies, towards the WHO goals of promoting and protecting mental health, transforming the way we care for and support those in need.

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